

EHMA 2024.

Shaping and managing
innovative health ecosystems

5-7 June 2024 - Bucharest, Romania

ABSTRACT BOOK

Institutul Național de Management
al Serviciilor de Sănătate

The European Health Management Association

The European Health Management Association (EHMA) is a not-for-profit membership organisation. Active since 1982, our vision is excellent health management for a healthy Europe.

We support the spread of knowledge on effective health management. Our actions focus on health management capacity and capabilities and aim to support the successful implementation of health policy and practice. We are a recognised and respected amplifier of best practices in the evolution of health management, with a European and global reach. Through our efforts, we make a difference across Europe to improve health for all citizens.

We are open to all those committed to improving health and healthcare. We play a crucial role in engaging with the full European health management ecosystem. We are a highly accessible and well-established place where people can debate and engage in issues that affect them, where they feel they can advocate for change, and find solutions. Through our members and networks, we reach local, regional, national, and international levels.

About the EHMA Conference

The EHMA Conference is Europe's preeminent conference on health management. Each year it gathers the full healthcare ecosystem, including health managers and leaders, healthcare professionals, researchers, academics, industry representatives, and decision-makers from Europe, and beyond.

The EHMA Conference provides a platform to discuss the latest health management research, tools and evidence from renowned researchers, academics and professionals. It is concerned on translating research into practice. It creates opportunities for dialogue and exchange on solutions to ensure the sustainability and resilience of health systems.

The European Health Management Conference 2024

EHMA 2024 is the 29th edition of our Annual Conference. This year's conference theme 'Shaping and managing innovative health ecosystems' encompasses the entire spectrum of health megatrends. From the digital transformation of healthcare systems and services, to the ever-growing importance of sustainability, and the evolving skill sets required by the healthcare workforce, we aim to explore how the health sector is adapting to these changes.

We emphasise an ecosystem approach, promoting collaboration among stakeholders. Our aim is to facilitate dialogue on how different health care actors can work together and leverage each other's strengths to drive innovation and address pressing challenges.

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Health care between Artificial Intelligence and 'nature-based' solution - finding a sustainable pathways

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Artificial intelligence and digitalisation has arisen as a subject in many areas and segments of human existence, and it is a particularly important issue in the health sector.

In the EU Year of Skills, the importance of digital skills on one hand, and sustainability skills on the other, within the health sector is particularly highlighted (as is confirmed by the BeWell project). And while great progress is being made in the field of technologies intended for the health sector, at the same time the risks and threats in nature due to climate change, catastrophic events and challenges in the energy supply, but also water (thus essential resources for the functioning of health systems) are intensifying.

The 21st century of high technologies and the digital revolution seems unable to fence itself off and overcome basic challenges and threats to functioning. On the one hand, the health sector is being intensively modernised, and on the other, the fragility of the health sector is growing.

Due to the pandemic, we have seen how little time it takes for systems to be disrupted. Climate change and catastrophic events can cause faster and more intense disruption ("earthquake") of the health sector. Lack of electricity and water, even on a smaller scale, can cause huge consequences.

At the same time, disruption in the production of medicines and in the supply of drugs can be the result of difficulties in the pharmaceutical industry, but also due to natural disasters and humanitarian disasters (which, unfortunately, is present today in several hotspots). The lack of medicines, on the one hand, and their ineffectiveness as a threat (for example of antimicrobial resistance - AMR) is recognised as a challenge not only for the health sector, but also wider as a challenge for One health approach

For example, Serbia experienced disrupted functioning of the health care system due to floods, difficulties in electricity supply in the relatively recent past. These and similar experiences should be an inspiration for system adaptation and improvement of resilience.

It is therefore important to consider the possibilities of treatment and assistance even in the disturbed conditions that the future may bring us. Thinking about "nature-based" and alternative ("nature inspired") solutions in healthcare, as well as in other sectors, is imposed. Preparedness for situations that are unwanted, but not impossible, is very necessary. Taking into account various future scenarios it is important to consider "nature based" and "nature inspired" solutions for strengthening resilience of the healthcare system, as well as preparedness of the health professionals and population.

The imperative that is imposed, is that we need to develop readiness, awareness and skills in two directions: in the direction of improving digital skills and sustainability skills following modern technologies. On the other hand, during the education process, learning towards "nature based" "nature inspired" and alternative solutions must not be neglected. It is important to be ready to apply both approaches sometimes in parallel to keep the health care system as stable as possible, in case of different, but very realistic and possible future scenarios.